

GOALS AND TASKS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Norqulov Bekzod Khurramovich

Denau Entrepreneurship and Pedagogical Institute

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ANNOTATION

The article explores the multifaceted goals of teaching foreign languages, specifically English, in high school settings. It argues that the objectives of foreign language education are heavily influenced by societal demands and educational policies, which evolve over time. Historically, the focus in the mid-20th century was on listening comprehension, while modern approaches prioritize a broader set of skills. The article identifies four primary goals: communicative (practical), general educational, educational, and developmental.

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada o'rtta maktab sharoitida chet tillarini, xususan, ingliz tilini o'rgatishning ko'p qirrali maqsadlari o'rganiladi. Unda ta'kidlanishicha, chet tili ta'limining maqsadlariga vaqt o'tishi bilan rivojlanib boruvchi ijtimoiy talablar va ta'lim siyosati katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tarixiy jihatdan, 20-asrning o'rtalarida asosiy e'tibor tinglashni tushunishga qaratilgan bo'lsa, zamonaviy yondashuvlar kengroq ko'nikmalar to'plamiga ustuvor ahamiyat beradi. Maqolada to'rtta asosiy maqsad aniqlangan: kommunikativ (amaliy), umumiy ta'lim, ta'lim va rivojlanish.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье исследуются многогранные цели преподавания иностранных языков, в частности английского, в старших классах. В нем утверждается, что на цели образования на иностранных языках сильно влияют социальные требования и образовательная политика, которые со временем развиваются. Исторически сложилось так, что в середине 20-го века основное внимание уделялось пониманию на слух, в то время как современные подходы отдают приоритет более широкому набору навыков. В статье выделены четыре первостепенные цели: коммуникативная (практическая), общеобразовательная, образовательная, развивающая.

The social order, conditions, and policy of the society always determine the work and purpose of the general educational institution and school. The demand of the society affects the clarification of the practical, communicative goal. The goals of making a foreign language vary depending on the development and development of society. Teaching a foreign language in high school has its own goals. We need to figure it out in advance. Knowing these goals affects the creation and development of a foreign language teaching methodology course. This course directs and adapts its methodology to the implementation of these goals. Otherwise, the goals cannot be realized. In the 40—50s of the 20th century, the goal of teaching listening comprehension was the leader in our schools, and speaking was only formed. Now they have changed depending on the demand of the times and society. The goals of teaching a foreign language determine the content, means, methods, principles of teaching. The goals of teaching a foreign language in high school have their own characteristics.

I. V. Rakhmanov's teacher L. V. Developing Szczerba's opinion, some of the issues of teaching a foreign language in secondary schools define the main goals of teaching a foreign language in his article«. He says that the goals of foreign language teaching are general education, education and communication, as well as the use of acquired skills and abilities for other purposes. This communication, communicative or practical goal is distinguished from the goals of teaching

other educational subjects. A communicative or practical goal means teaching students to understand and accept the opinions of others orally and in writing and to express their thoughts orally and in writing. Further expanding this, we can define information as a new tool - students' oral, written reception, understanding and oral, written return of information through English. Taking into account the above, teaching foreign languages is carried out 1) practical or communicative, 2) general education, 3) education, 4) and I. V. According to Rakhmanov, he sets the goals of using the acquired skills and abilities for other purposes, that is, development. General educational, educational, developmental goals occur in the implementation of the communicative goal. Let's look at these 4 goals later:

1. Communicative (practical) purpose:

Through this goal, students will develop skills and abilities in English language materials. Students should be able to independently use lexical and grammatical pronunciation materials in speech. English speaking and writing skills are formed.

2. General educational purpose:

Through this goal, to further develop students' thinking, to receive and provide information from the English language, to gain a deeper understanding of the English language, to gain new knowledge about the English language, and to gain understanding and information about the history, literature, and culture of the people of the country where the language is being studied. It is understood to expand the worldview of students. To develop students' understanding, thinking, and broadening their worldview will be at the expense of a foreign language or in English.

3. Educational purpose:

This goal is to provide international, moral and aesthetic education and to educate the attitude to work in the foreign language — English class. Of course, these are done by analyzing the subject of English speech, the content of English texts through English — materials.

4. Developmental goal:

This goal determines the guidelines for learning and teaching students. It develops the skills of analyzing language facts, summarizing, drawing independent conclusions, listening, and speaking. He teaches by imagining, creating a speech situation, that logic is connected in speech, the ability to think independently, to understand the meaning of words, to work independently with dictionaries and manuals, and to optional activities, develops independent preparation for extracurricular activities, their transfer. The above four goals always complement each other, communicate with each other. These four goals should be implemented through English language materials and speech activities taught and returned in each lesson. On the goals of teaching foreign languages in 1947 L. V. Shcherba, in 1950 A. N. Manighetti, in 1965 I. V. Rakhmanov, in 1970 V. S. Setlin, in 1971 O. I. Moskalskaya dwelled in her manuals and articles. Next time I with this issue. L. Bim was also engaged. In his opinion, it is necessary to take a comprehensive approach to the implementation of practical, educational, educational and developmental goals of teaching foreign languages. I. L. According to Bim, the practical goal is to teach communication in a foreign language directly and through books. He says that the last goal or last practical result in teaching a foreign language is to receive and return extralinguistic information through acquired linguistic material.

Taking this idea into account, the goals are divided into 2 groups.

- Formation of skills and abilities through linguistic information;

- Formation of skills and abilities through extralinguistic information;

I. L. Bim divides speech activities into listening comprehension, speaking, reading, writing goals, each paragraph (Lesson), lesson categories, individual parts of the lesson, and each movement is divided into listening comprehension, speaking, reading, and writing tasks.

Pupils and students are required to be able to accept, understand and express English thoughts orally and in writing when they graduate from school. I. A. Bim understands the content of teaching and the content of the subject separately. By the content of teaching, it defines the process of reading and teaching. In order to achieve the set goal faster through the content of teaching, it is necessary to organize the linguistic material methodically. The content of the foreign language subject is a selected and clearly organized educational material for the specified purpose. Currently, the content of foreign language teaching in secondary schools means: the nature and scope of knowledge, materials, exercises and skills determined by the goals and tasks of education received by schoolchildren. When determining the content of the subject, it should not be forgotten that the general requirement of 2 and their interdependence:

1. The requirement to achieve or not to achieve our goal of the selected teaching content;
2. This is the requirement of students' inability to master or master the content of the chosen teaching in our specific conditions. Taking into account these 2 requirements, it is possible to determine the content of the subject of foreign language teaching. In the project of the high school foreign language program, the content of English language teaching is determined, each foreign language teacher is obliged to organize his work based on this program.

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